

Brazilian Modern Architecture: climatic Adaptation Principles

Introduction

There are several elements which characterise the modern architecture in Brazil. They represented, beyond the formal language and aesthetic value, the materialisation of inherent concepts to good architecture, which adapted itself to the local climate.

At the beginning of the 20th century as a response to the proliferation in Brazil of the new styles from abroad, the so-called "neo-colonial style" was created. This style was a result of a movement promoted by some architects who intended to recover national roots of Brazilian architecture through colonial architecture language. It came up as Lúcio Costa said, "with good intention" arguing that "if we have to fake, we should do it faking what is ours" (COSTA, 1975:98).

However these architects chose as formal reference the 18th century architecture which, wrongly, could represent "our architecture" despising models already transformed that could mean indeed a new Brazilian architecture that was being built since the middle of the 19th century in diverse parts of the country. This architecture, most residential, indicated a specific typology with constructive elements adapted to the climate and therefore able to giving better salutary and comfort to the users than the colonial architecture.

The error of the neo-colonial architects was somehow redeemed when Lucio Costa and others architects started to develop the so called Brazilian Modern architecture once they recovered formal concepts and constructive elements already tested and approved by use which could be identified as "national" due to their adequacy to the hot humid climate of the country.

Two of these principles or basic concepts are: the open character of the architecture and the integration interior/exterior specific of certain housing typologies either rural or built in urban peripheries since the middle of the 19th century. From this time are also the external elements of solar protection, the lattice windows, the trellis as well as glazed tiles applied to external walls, which were recovered and used in the modern architecture built in Brazil.

It is important to look at this principles and concepts and how those elements were used in order to understand tropical climate, as well as the appropriation and transformations undertaken by them in their utilisation and articulation as elements and solutions within Brazilian modern architecture.

Before analysing, from the climate point of view, the utilisation of these elements in some outstanding examples of Brazilian modern architecture, they will be studied regarding their adequacy to the climate and the transformations, from old to modern, suffered by them due to new formal concepts and building materials used in Brazil.

Outsider Influences

As Philip Goodwin (1943:81) asserts it is clear that Brazil has been dominated by a great cultural influence from France, for since the second decade of the 19th century the presence of the French Artistic Mission in Brazil was highly responsible for the spread and taste in arts and architecture. The members of the Academy were the idealizers and organisers of the first Academy of Fine Arts, in Rio de Janeiro, where the first undergraduate course of architecture was later created. Since the middle of the 19th and beginning of the 20th century influences through many instances of neo-classical and eclectic architecture spread in the most important cities and in the capitals of the Brazilian states.

The pre existences and this flexibility to adopt international influences made it carrier for the ideas of Le Corbusier to be welcomed and applied by the young architects responsible for the project of the Ministério de Educação e Saúde of Rio de Janeiro (1936 – 1943). This building although was not the first manifestation of modern architecture in Brazil it is, undoubtedly, the great reference of the modern movement in Brazil. As Henrique Mindlin (1956: 196) states: "...is the most striking symbol of modern architecture in Brazil and the first application on a monumental scale, of Le Corbusier's ideas.

The adoption of new ideas and the need of an architecture, responding to the changes and modernisation occurring in the country, and somehow these ideas supported innovation in the very governmental machinery. Without doubt these factors were determinant for new building patterns

grounded themselves in a cultural as well as proper climatic reality, that allows, without being arrogant assert, that: "Brazilian Modernism is, simultaneously, an effort of actualisation and a rediscovery of our cultural roots, a renovation within a tradition" (MORAIS, in ALCÂNTARA, 1997:93).

The Search Of "Appropriate" Solutions

"Although the first modern impetus came from imports, very soon Brazil founded its proper way" (GOODWIN, 1943: 84). This proper way does not resume to the utilisation of "(...) innovations destined to avoid the heat and the lightened reflexes in glass surfaces, by means of external special *quebra luzes*." (GOODWIN 1943: 84). Much more than that, one can dare to assert, some concepts and *bio-climatic* principles are inserted in many of the founded solutions: concepts as cross ventilation with specific zones, of in and out ventilation, of fragmented spaces enlarged and integrated with the exterior, intermediary spaces of protection and connection with the mild nature of the place, besides other elements that constitute the skin of the buildings, which will be detailed later on.

Enlarged spaces and zones of integration exterior-interior

The enlarged spaces on colonial architecture determined either by the great height of the rooms or by the little fragmentation of the spaces are also present in modern Brazilian architecture. These large areas allow great cubature of air facilitating thermal changes among diverse air layers in the internal environment.

This concept of large room height is extensively used in modern architecture via the introduction of the mezzanine. For instance, in the work of Oscar Niemeyer they are mainly found in outstanding buildings such as the Palácio da Alvorada (1957), the Palácio da Indústria in Ibiapuera Park (1953) or the Cassino da Pampulha (1942). One can also list the Estação de Hidroaviões (1937-1938) by Atílio Correia Lima, the Aeroporto Santos Dumont (1937-1944) by the brothers Marcelo and Milton Roberto, the Faculdade de Arquitetura e Urbanismo (1961-1969) by Vilanova Artigas and the Escola de Minas e Metalurgia (1960-1967) by Oswaldo Bratke, the two last belonging to the Universidade de São Paulo. Besides these examples, many others buildings give an idea of the amplitude and flowness of the space and air through the double height of some areas.

Among other smaller buildings, notably residences, double height spaces can be seen in Cunha Lima House (1958) by the architect Joaquin Guedes, in Caetano Miani House by Paulo Mendes da Rocha and J.E. de Gennaro from 1962, in João Paulo de

Miranda Neto (1953) by Ligia Fernandes built in Maceió, in George Hime Country House (1949) designed by Henrique Mindlin and the own house of Italo Eugênio Mauro in São Paulo (1947).

The other constant reference of traditional Brazilian architecture is the indoor/outdoor integration through multiples openings pierced in the façades and by the *varandas* around the building. This space, acts as chock absorber of the thermal impact on the walls as well as shadow and protection zone against the direct action of the sun on people. This space where one feels sheltered and it expands the relations of the very building, interacting directly with the nature of the surrounding space, with its maximum enlargement in the *pilotis*.

In modern architecture the veranda has a character of great protection and formal expression of the covering as one can see in the Supremo Tribunal Federal (1958-1960) or in the Palácio do Planalto (1958-1960) by Niemeyer where the lengthening of the roof form terraces all around and the body of the building is halted and free in its interior integrated to the exterior through the mild transparency of the glass. Another huge example of this protection of lengthening roof is the Museu de Arte Moderna (1954) by Affonso Reidy. Here the building basically hang in the large roof that shelter itself and the exterior spaces invade the covered area resulting in shadowy gardens.

One could give innumerable examples of architecture in Brazil where the integration of inside and outside can be seen, for instance several buildings by Lucio Costa, Rino Levi, Cerqueira Cezar and Oswaldo Bratke among others. A good example is the house of Oscar Niemeyer where the built mass is sheltered by the sinuous curves of the cover forming a continuous veranda integrating, through the floor, open spaces and covered spaces. These verandas are also present in many residential high rise buildings such as the Edifício Prudência (1944) by Rino Levi and Roberto Cerqueira Cezar, the Edifício Louveira (1946) by Vilanova Artigas e Carlos Cascaldi, the buildings that compose the Parque Guinle (1950) by Lúcio Costa. The verandas of both areas social and service of a residential compound designed by Gregori Warchavchik in São Paulo (1939) also deserve mention as well as his first work in Brazil, his own house, designed in 1928, where the architect refers to the "L" shaped veranda of the *casa grande* (manor house) of the colonial period.

The utilisation of these intermediary areas between inside and outside presented huge advantages in a hot and humid climate that dominates a great part of Brazilian territory. Besides the promotion of shadow and its effectiveness blocked of direct solar radiation, the integrated areas facilitates the flow of

the air inside the building, allowing the flowing off of the wind, that with low pressure, easily penetrates in the building through the windows facing the veranda. This shadowy area also serves to diminish the natural light intensity in the interior, rooms reducing the effect of dazzling of this light and makes, principally, an intermediary space that integrates the building with the nature all around.

Besides protecting the walls and creating shadow the veranda works as a dispersed of heat and that captures the breeze and facilitates its penetration in the building. In the same way as in the protected corridors and sidewalks generated by the *marquises* or by overhangings of buildings over *pilotis* they created a continuous shadow in the public space.

Building on *pilotis* promotes sheltered circulation from the sun, and ameliorates the quality of the urban environment from the point of view of ventilation and salutary, by allowing greater flowing and dispersion of air at the level of the street. It also reduces the levels of dampness of the floors and in it has the great advantage of isolating the walls of the building from the natural action of the rising damp through capillary. It eliminates the residual water added by this process to the walls of the ground floor, there by it reduces and controls the dampness inside the building besides contributing to a better conservation of the bases of walls and generally speaking to the building as a whole.

External Walls Treatment

The constitutive elements of the external walls or the surface treatment of the buildings, includes openings and closing elements, with are extremely responsible for thermal changing between the building and external environment. Through them one can promote an architecture that works passively with the climate guaranteeing desirable levels of comfort inside the buildings principally when the climate is mild without great thermal amplitudes as it does occur in the most part of Brazilian territory.

Brise-soleil and *quebra-sol* vs. glass panels

Undoubtedly the influence of Le Corbusier over the group coordinated by Lúcio Costa for designing the Ministério da Educação e Saúde(1936), in Rio de Janeiro, was remarkable and brought conclusive outcomes to the modern architecture built subsequently in Brazil. From this influence stands out the attitude of searching solutions in building materials and characteristic elements of local constructions like designing buildings and façades considering the climate. As examples one can mention the protection against solar radiation by *brise soleil* elements, firstly developed by Le Corbusier for a project in Argel (1933) but formerly used at the

façade of the Associação Brasileira de Imprensa by M.M. Roberto designed and built in Rio de Janeiro between 1936 and 1938.

Elements of exterior protection applied on the openings had already been tested and its efficiency was well-known in Brazil. To correct or diminishing thermal effects and problems originated by massive use of English glass windows or sash windows, that became a substitute to the *gelosias* from the second decade of the 19th century on, when the *esteiras da china* including started to be used. It was a sort of exterior movable curtain, made of small horizontal juxtaposed slabs, fastened laterally by strings that, when closed allowed regular intermediary open spaces between them. Superimposed to the casement fastened by the outer side at the upper part of the openings, these elements assured not only privacy inside the rooms but also and principally they allowed the efficient control of the natural light excess and the direct solar radiation through the glass windows.

Certainly these external curtains, which appeared by the middle of the 19th century as can be seen in engravings and photographs of some cities as Salvador and Recife were the harbingers, in Brazil, of the lattice windows that worked as the future *brise soleil*. Superimposed to the windows they hindered the direct solar radiation penetration until guaranteeing ventilation through its gaps, inside the house.

The use of *brise soleil*, allow the great advantage of belonging to the body of the building and formally defining it. The decision of using them might be incorporated in the designing decisions, for its correct localisation, to assure the efficiency on the protection element of the openings as well its function as barrier to the direct sunlight, and its of extreme importance the correct design during the elaboration of the project.

With the localisation of the *brise-soleil* or *quebra-sol* superimposed to the façades, externally to the curtain wall, it is much more efficient from the thermal point of view, than any other element or barrier that eventually may be used inside the openings. In this way it blocks the direct action of the solar radiation, reducing significantly the solar radiation thermal effect on the glass, known as "green house effect".

The use of *quebra-sol* in façades might be correctly designed considering the latitude of the place, the apparent course of the sun in the sky, the orientation of the façades, the topography of the plot, the characteristics of the surrounds and the different positions of the sun during the year in order to guarantee its efficacy. All these factors might be considered to a correct definition of the position and dimensions of the slabs of the *quebra-sol* otherwise it will happen, as we can see in some build-

ings were they appear indistinctly in façades that receive little or no sun or even the orientation of the plates which instead of protecting they serve as captor of direct solar radiation. In these cases the brises loose its function and turn to be mere superimposed tridimensional objects to give movement to the façade and illusions of good architecture.

In Brazilian modern architecture one can find an extreme formal diversity in the way *brise soleil* are applied regarding the direction and the dimension of its plates. Examples vary since the huge vertical panels in concrete, as in Associação Brasileira de Imprensa building, already cited, by M.M. Roberto or in the Aeroporto Santos Dumont by the same group, to the small attached slabs of the Parque Guinle buildings (1948-1954) by Lúcio Costa in Rio de Janeiro or in the alternated panels with narrow slabs proposed by Paulo Antunes Ribeiro to the Caramuru building in Salvador (1946) until the movable panels designed by Alvaro Vital Brasil for the Banco da Lavoura built in Belo Horizonte in 1951. Regarding horizontal plates, one can mention, among others, the movable panels constituted by small slabs, similar to the ones of *esteira-da-china*, used in the Marques de Oval building by M.M. Roberto (1953-1955) in Rio de Janeiro, the movable panels of asbetos with large width and length equal to the ones of its windows in the Ministério de Educação e Saúde, the panels of the Bus Terminal in Londrina, by Vilanova Artigas (1951) and the fixed plates of the Cooperativa e Lavanderia of the Conjunto Residencial Pedregulho by Affonso Reidy. Another important reference by Reidy is the extreme movements resulted from the fixed and movable *quebra-sois* simultaneously using horizontal and vertical plates with diverse proportions, posed to the west façade of the Instituto de Previdência do Estado da Guanabara headquarters (1957).

Lattice window with diverse variations is another element that largely has been used in the modern architecture in Brazil. This type of frame was already extensively used in the country since the last half of the 19th century. Its adoption meant the integration of the wooden strips of the *esteiras-da-china* to the window frame. These wooden elements counterpoising or substituting the glass casement corrects the utilisation of glass windows in two crucial aspects, from a climate point of view. They allow the direct and diffuse radiation control and the in and out of air inside the rooms. The parallel plates that may be fixed or preferably movable allow total control of quantities of ventilation and natural lighting inside the building through the openings formed by the continuous intervals.

Besides the correct utilisation of lattice windows modern architecture also brought the innovation to

use huge glass panels to the façades of Brazilian buildings. The employment of curtain walls bring serious troubles to the higo-thermal and luminous character in a hot and humid climate. For that they should be avoided at any situation in a climate like this due to the green house effect, already mentioned, as well as the dazzling effect resulting of the excessive natural light coming inside.

"Thus glass transmits radiation in a selective manner, permitting solar radiation to penetrate into the building to be absorbed by the internal surfaces and objects and to elevate their temperature. But the heated surfaces emit radiation at peak intensity with a wavelength of about 10 microns and this radiation cannot be transmitted outwards through the glass owing to its opaqueness to this wavelength. (GIVONI, 1976:234)

In this way either the radiation by retransmission of objects or the transmission given by the users of the rooms remain inside generating an internal overheating. This heat only can be dissipated if the ventilation openings are sufficient. Generally the glass panels allow only small apertures in relation to the total opening what certainly bring great troubles from the thermal comfort point of view in hot climates. This leads to the necessity of introducing artificial mechanisms of environmental refrigeration which many times would have been, totally dispensable if the façades were properly treated.

Another problem caused by the curtain walls is the excessive entrance of natural light within the building which is usually corrected by fabric curtain or interior barriers that do not eliminate the green house effect and contribute to increase the thermal charge inside by the thermal process mentioned above. At present an attempt to diminish this problem is obtained by the utilisation of filtering pellicle of light and chromatic treatments applied to the glass. This modifies the quality and quantity of natural light inside the buildings. However these solutions offer becomes are very expensive and besides it only partially solves the problem.

One can mention many instances of correct uses of lattice windows and glass applied to modern architecture in Brazil as the employment of horizontal pivoting windows like the ancient ones used by Gregori Warchavichik in the Max Graf House in São Paulo (1928-1929), where the very window serves as a barrier for the solar radiation while permitting the natural ventilation inside the room, or the fixed lattices used in the Casa Modernista by the same author in 1929-1930.

Other examples worth while mentioning are the façade of movable lattice used in the George Hime

country house (1949) by Henrique Mindlin, the residences for officials and teachers of the Centro Técnico da Aeronáutica by Oscar Niemeyer, in São José dos Campos (1947) and the large lattice or tilting windows of the Instituto Nacional do Câncer by Rino Levi and Roberto Cerqueira César in São Paulo, built in 1954.

The “Combogós” or enlarged trellis

Another element developed and largely employed in Brazilian architecture after the thirties is the *combogó*. This element possibly originated in Pernambuco is a pierced slab of ceramic or chinaware which has the hollow area bigger than the massive one.

Its function may be compared to the wooden trellis of the old *gelosias* that filled up the window's openings or the beautiful *muxarabis* of the Brazilian colonial architecture. These, although blocking the entrance of direct solar radiation and allowing certain ventilation through the interstices of the wooden frame, resulted in small openings that darkened too much the interior of the room. The resultant open space was smaller than the closing area making difficult the penetration of external ventilation and the free circulation of air inside the houses. This element worked better to withdrawal or flowing off the internal air.

On the contrary the *combogó* solves these problems and may be considered as an enlarged trellis. Made of clay or cement they present few structuring material and larger apertures. This empty and full relation gives to them a great advantage, from the ventilation point of view, for it permits a free circulation either at the entrance or at the withdraw of the air inside the building. According the pattern arrangement and its localisation in the façade in relation to the relative sun positions in the sky they can minimise or even hinder the entrance of direct solar radiation inside the rooms. Therefore a west wall of *combogó* is much more effective from the thermal point of view, than an open wall, while it offers shadow and works perfectly when these openings are directed to the air exit.

With the direct solar radiation occurring in this pierced wall this half-open space creates a *heated air-mattress* that works as an air sucker through the apertures of the intermediary wall between this limited area by the *combogó* and the interior space. This means, it produces a *chimney effect* facilitating ventilation in the opposing exterior wall.

The glazed tiles on the façades

Glazed tiles used as facing material of walls in Brazilian architecture is an issue that deserves to be studied due to its large employment. Not only as a

compositional element since colonisation times till the architectural modern movement in Brazil, but also as an impermeable isolating facing material for walls and façades in high rainy regions.

Regarding thermal aspects the glazed tiles smooth surface has a function of reflecting solar radiation that is greater than that of plasterwork. Therefore theoretically, it absorbs less radiation and it has a density that presents a major thermal inertia that is larger than that of plaster. The result is that the tiled wall absorbs less quantity of thermal energy. Consequently the internal surface of the wall transmits less quantity of heat to the interior of the building, when compared in a similar period of time, to an equal wall without tiled revetment.

When tiled walls are used in a hot humid climate like the ones of Brazilian coast, its may cause problems of bad indoor comfort. When the façades are washed by the rainfalls, great part of the water is absorbed by the joints, between the tiles, mainly if they haven't been treated with hydrous repellent material. This water infiltrated into the wall, and has to difficulties to evaporate to the exterior due to the impermeable revetment. Instead it evaporates through the internal face, accumulating the level of relative air humidity inside the building that already was high in the first place.

Besides being expressive, the reuse of glazed tiles on the walls of the Ministério da Educação e Saúde, redefines a recovering of cultural roots. Beyond its useful functions it carries a powerful symbolic meaning as an architectural monument, demonstrating it a renewal of cultural and constructive tradition representative of the country.

Conclusion

Brazilian modern architecture stands out in the national and international scenario for its differentiated repertoire. It appropriates some concepts firstly developed in other countries, adapting and intermingling them with needs, concepts and constructive elements already existing in Brazil. It develops without copying mimetically, and elaborates a repertoire based on formal and constructive responses that adapt themselves to the place where it works passively with the climate somehow obeying to *bio-climatic* basis.

It is necessary to say that many times the protection elements and the treatment of the building skin which represented the Brazilian modern architecture sometimes used empirically and other times were integrated to the façades searching to create more aesthetic than functional expression. Nowadays it is necessary to rescue these constructive elements through a correct evaluation of its use. However is also necessary to promote the diffusion of these fundamental concepts and patterns once they

can work very well in an architecture that functions passively in favour of the climate and in consonance with energy economy necessary to the development in this new millennium.

This process that suffered an abrupt solution of continuity in the middle of the sixties is basically absent because concepts and constructive patterns in Brazil nowadays are adopted the proliferate exogenous models, despite the typical and specific conditions of the country. Architecture that is good to a temperate climate certainly does not to workable in a tropical one.

The proliferation of exogenous models is present in the globalized world. "Extreme epidermal hedonism" dominates architectural works where the dictatorship of glass and transparency rules, brought by an expressionless architecture. Some months after a new building appears in an International magazine or Internet one can see it emerging as a clone built in our tropical cities. The technical patterns that, many times, are inside the original are not transferred to the copy which lacks the rigor purpose determinant of the original, where technology was incorporated overall in order to respond not only to formal and utilisation questions but, certainly, to the milieu that determined it. One builds a standardised international architecture that is absorbed without minimal architectural criteria of analysis, because generally even in Brazil, it is not undertaken an evaluation of energy costs and maintenance of artificial conditioning equipments as well as of the damaging effects on the environment regarding either the building or the people. From this lack of adaptation to the region peculiarities results the unsatisfactory solutions introduced through artificial climatisation.

The technological development allows that these buildings are adapted climatically by the introduction of mechanical equipments, able to transform the internal hydrothermal conditions. The constant use of artificial conditioning brings, in time, irreversible damages to the human thermal regulator system as well as breathing problems caused mainly by development and proliferation of fungi and micro-organisms inside of these refrigeration systems.

Most of the developed countries search alternatives to adapt buildings to the climate with low costs of electrical and human energy. But in Brazil the proliferation of a glass transparent box architecture, or worse, the black or dark glass boxes, with extravagant plastering and inadequate openings dominates the new architecture. This demands a massive utilisation of mechanical conditioners with high costs of energy, if even heats the external environment instead of using and taking advantage of the extremely favourable and beneficial conditions of the tropical climate on Brazil.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Alcântara, Dora. (1997). *Azulejos na cultura luso – brasileira*. Rio de Janeiro, IPHAN.
- Bonduki Nabil, Portinho Carmen. (2000) *Affonso Eduardo Reidy*. Editorial Blau e Instituto Lina e P. M. Bardi.
- Bruand, Yves. (1997). *Arquitetura contemporânea no Brasil*. 3ª edição, São Paulo: Editora Perspectiva S. A.
- Costa, Lúcio. (1995) *Lúcio Costa: registro de uma vivência*. São Paulo: Empresa das Artes/UNB.
- Givoni, B. (1981) *Man, Climate and Architecture*. Applied Science Publishers Ltd, London, 2ª edicion.
- Goodwin, Philip L. (1943). *Brazil Builds: Architecture New and Old 1652 - 1942*. New York, MOMA.
- Hitchcock, Henry-Russell. (1994). *Die Architektur des 19. und 20. Jahrhunderts*. München: Aries Verlag.
- Mindlin, Henrique, E. (1956). *Modern Architecture in Brazil*. Rio de Janeiro/Amsterdam: Colibris Editora Ltda.
- Penedo, Alexandre. (1997) *Arquitetura Moderna em São José dos Campos*. São José dos Campos, São Paulo: A. Penedo.
- Reidy, A. E. (1985) *Affonso Eduardo Reidy*. Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Rio de Janeiro. Solar GrandJean de Montigny: Rio de Janeiro: O Solar:Index.
- Segawa, H. e DOURADO. G. M. (1997) *Oswaldo Arthur Bratke*. São Paulo: ProEditores.

KEYWORDS

modern architecture; building technology; tropical environmental design; solar control

Griselda Klüppel. Architect and Professor of the Department of Design in the Faculty of Architecture (Federal University of Bahia, Brazil); Specialist in Environmental Design (UFPB, Brazil); Master in Conservation (UFBA, Brazil). Currently is concluding the Doctoral thesis on the Brazilian domestic architecture changes related to its local climate (UPC, Spain). Co-author of the "*Manual de Conservação Preventiva para Edificações*" (Brazilian Heritage/IPHAN and UNESCO).